

Summary of 4th Base4NFDI Integration Workshop

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In a virtual workshop on 23 April 2026, representatives of NFDI consortia and team members of Base4NFDI's basic services discussed how to integrate a basic service, what resources are needed, and what challenges the integration can entail. A key focus of the workshop was aligning different perspectives and approaches to integrating basic services within the NFDI consortia. Three incubator projects from three different consortia were presented (presentations and summarised Q&A below). The presentations addressed both technical and organisational requirements from the consortia perspective as well as the service perspective.

Based on the presentations the participants could gain a clearer understanding of how to initiate integration processes, and they had the opportunity to engage directly with the service teams in six separated [breakout rooms](#). Additionally, another breakout room invited the participants to exchange experiences and challenges the NFDI consortia had and have in the integration phase.

Below you will find summaries of the various breakout rooms, as well as shared links and other useful materials to the relevant basic services.

Conclusion

- The workshop addressed ongoing integration challenges of basic services into NFDI consortia, while also highlighting **practical solutions**. A key takeaway was the **need for stronger alignment between consortia and service teams** to meet both technical and organisational requirements and enable smoother integration.
- Participants emphasised a **user-centric approach**, calling for tailored presentations, demos, and clearer communication to better meet the needs of diverse stakeholders and demonstrate the value of the services.
- While many consortia rely on helpdesks and designated contacts, insufficient internal communication remains a barrier. To improve this, more direct and **structured communication strategies** were proposed, including mailing lists, targeted outreach materials, product-oriented websites, and accessible “how-to” guides for non-technical users, alongside more **active engagement from consortia**.
- Finally, the workshop highlighted the importance of **strengthening cross-consortium collaboration** to tackle shared challenges, leverage synergies, and develop successful incubator models.

Based on the discussion the following **key actions for the Base4NFDI team for 2026/2027** have been defined:

- 1. Address the consortia more directly**
 - a. Action: set up a mailing list to improve communication strategies
 - b. Action: reach out to contact person within consortia directly
- 2. Put more weight on user perspective to address the diverse needs of developers, researchers, and communication staff**
 - a. Action: organise more demo sessions
 - b. Action: prepare more “How to” guides and discipline tailored presentations
 - c. Action: restructure website
- 3. Foster collaboration across consortia and with services to address shared challenges and leverage synergies**
 - a. Action: use incubator presentation to show address technical and organisational requirements and illustrate the value of an implemented service

Slides presented by Base4NFDI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19849712>

Incubator Presentations

NFDI4Chem / TS4NFDI, IAM4NFDI by Felix Bach

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19851726>

Text+ / Jupyter4NFDI by Florian Barth and Tim Kreuzer

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19852588>

NFDI4Earth / DMP4NFDI by Auriol Degbello and Bjarne Biskamp

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19852409>

Summarised Q&A

The Q&A session focused on both technical and organisational aspects of integrating and using Base4NFDI services within the NFDI consortia. One important discussion point concerned the handling of research data in RADAR4Chem. It was explained that datasets are archived as BagIt containers and that individual datasets currently have a maximum size limit of 600 GB due to the underlying bwDataArchive infrastructure. At the same time, participants learned that the actual size of datasets in chemistry can vary considerably, ranging from only a few kilobytes to several terabytes, depending on the research field. While many chemistry datasets are relatively small, theoretical chemistry may require the management of very large data collections.

Another topic was the introduction and usability of Jupyter4NFDI and the MONAPipe library. The speakers underlined that Jupyter4NFDI enables users to [directly access](#) Python resources and workflows without the need for local software installations. Participants asked how MONAPipe could be reused within the platform, and it was demonstrated that

users can access shared environments through JupyterHub instances and [dedicated documentation](#). The discussion also pointed to authentication and login issues related to IAM4NFDI and community access, highlighting that some integrations, such as the connection for NFDI4Earth, are still under development but expected to be available in the near future.

In addition to technical integration, participants discussed organisational workflows and communication structures for integrating basic services. Questions were raised about how consortia manage integration processes internally, distribute support requests, and allocate responsibilities. The responses showed that many consortia rely on helpdesk teams and designated contact persons to coordinate communication and answer service-related questions efficiently. Finally, the importance of user-centered communication was emphasized through the suggestion to develop personas for different target groups within NFDI, such as developers, researchers, and communication staff. Base4NFDI welcomed this idea and noted that [persona creation](#) and user story workshops are already being offered to services during their initialisation phase in order to better address diverse user needs and communication preferences.

Summaries Breakout Rooms

Room 1 - IAM4NFDI & ACC4NFDI

The discussion around the IAM4NFDI and Accounting4NFDI services were in a common room to draw attention to the idea of Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting as a 'triple A approach'. Users were mainly interested in the concept and organisation of virtual organisations (VOs). On the one hand consortia need to manage VOs and keep a close connection to the respective communities, while on the other hand, there are developments in the NFDI which will have an impact on this approach. IAM4NFDI offered technical counsel but pointed out that communities know themselves best. Also, an upcoming workshop about VOs was advertised.

The topic of accounting was also interesting for several participants. Though the team has only started with their work recently, ACC4NFDI invited interested stakeholders to join the requirement survey and interviews for the consortia.

Related materials:

About IAM4NFDI

- Service Website: <https://iam.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- Incubator Overview: <https://incubators.nfdi-aai.de/>
- Explainer video on [Youtube](#)
- IAM4NFDI at Service Roadshow on [Youtube](#)
- IAM4NFDI Service Onboarding Handbook, [Zenodo](#)

About Accounting4NFDI

- Service Landing page: <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/accounting4nfdi>

Room 2 - Jupyter4NFDI

It is well known that many communities and consortia have their own Jupyter resources and can access them easily. Nevertheless, there is generally growing interest in Jupyter4NFDI. For example, people have asked what the advantage of this service is compared to other installations. The service team introduced, for instance, the ability to integrate community data portals via storage mounts or Docker images. There are several other advantages, such as real-time collaboration, Binder functionality, and the easy management of workshops via Jupyter4NFDI. Last but not least, the integration of resources from NFDI providers—as has already been done with de.NBI and GWDG—allows for the perfect realisation of the One-NFDI concept through this service. The consortia are encouraged to test the service offering through additional incubators, as was done for the presented MONApipe use case.

Related materials:

- Login [JupyterHub](#)
- [Repo2Docker feature](#)
- Jupyter4NFDI Discussions at [GitHub](#)

About Jupyter4NFDI

- Service Website: <https://nfdi-jupyter.de/>
- Use Case Overview: <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/community/use-cases/>
- Jupyter4NFDI at Service Roadshow on [Youtube](#)

Room 3 - DMP4NFDI

This breakout session, made up of primarily already existing cooperation partners (NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Cat) of DMP4NFDI, began with a short presentation by the DMP team on their offerings. The remaining time was used to discuss information flows between Base4NFDI and the consortia, as well as internally within consortia. Regarding the former, the personal preference was shared that information from Base4NFDI is best distributed via mailinglists; regarding the latter, experience was shared that, usually, individual persons bring up their interest in a basic service in a TA/consortium meeting in a bottom-up manner, which is then jointly discussed and approved or denied. Also, bilateral conversations are used to share information and discuss specific questions. Integration work seems to happen with rather less and even only individual persons, only including a wider audience (e.g. management) when necessary. Within a consortium, the information flow about existing collaborations with basic services is not always sufficient. Especially NFDI4Cat mentioned that financial and time resources are tight due to the budget cuts in funding, which makes collaborations with basic services not always feasible and dependent on personal motivation and contributions.

The session's take-away messages:

- Base4NFDI service information needs to reach infrastructure staff to foster bottom-up-initiated collaboration. Ideal format and content might be individual, but needs to be evaluated.
- Collaborations with our basic services may fail due to missing resources and more pressing priorities within the consortia.

Related materials:

- [DMP4NFDI](#)
- [Incubator projects](#)

About DMP4NFDI

- Service Website: <https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- Incubator Overview: <https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/incubator/>
- DMP4NFDI at Service Roadshow on [Youtube](#)
- DMP4NFDI Demo Session on [Youtube](#)

Room 4 - PID4NFDI

The group had a positive discussion environment and covered a wide range of topics in regards to Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), from political and safety issues to very specific matters. Below are the three core take aways:

- 1) **Service concept:** The PID4NFDI team consults users in selecting the best fit PID system as well as technically implementing PIDs and metadata management, and offers support in questions towards integration. Therefore, they started the [PID Selection Tool](#) and [PID Cook Book](#) and published their [landscape analysis](#).
- 2) **Community needs:** There is a desire for support in phasing out siloed solutions, whilst at the same time avoiding the creation of dependencies on handles. There is a need to retain autonomy in the management of PIDs while simultaneously allowing external parties the opportunity to reuse them.
- 3) **Ways of communication:** The attendees requested to get regularly updated about the status of the service development. A critical point was the decentralised and sometimes outdated information about the development status of the service. The outreach events of the service team were therefore very helpful. Users are always welcome to communicate their needs to the PID team, so that training and outreach material, workshops or other formats can be developed to match the needs of the users.

Related materials:

- Umfrage zu PID Providern in NFDI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15689799>
- <https://www.dpid.org/working-group>
- <https://www.softwareheritage.org/software-hash-identifier-swhid/>
<https://docs.ipfs.tech/concepts/content-addressing/>

- PID Metaresolver: <https://pidmr.argo.grnet.gr/>
- PID selection tool: <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/pidtool/>
- Cookbook and PID provider overview for more information: <https://pid4nfdi-training.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/get-pid/providers/>

About PID4NFDI

- Service Website: <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- Use Case Overview: <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/community/use-cases/>
- PID4NFDI at Service Roadshow on [Youtube](#)

Room 5 - RDMTraining4NFDI

The discussion focused on collaboration between RDM Training and the NFDI consortia, especially KonsortSWD. Key topics included the development of quality indicators and certification criteria for RDM training materials. Feedback on these has already been sought from the community. Challenges mentioned included fragmented communication, overlapping responsibilities and administrative hurdles at universities.

The RDM Training team presented their future work on seven use cases, integration phases, evaluation processes and best practice development. Participants agreed that continued exchange and cross-consortium collaboration will be essential going forward.

At a higher level, the group discussed the merit of having appointed people in consortia who deal with Base4NFDI services and keep track of communication.

Related materials:

About RDMTraining4NFDI

- Service Website: <https://rdmt.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- RDMT4NFDI at Service Roadshow on [Youtube](#)

Room 6 - TS4NFDI & KGI4NFDI

The breakout session initially gave the TS4NFDI and KGI4NFDI teams space to exchange directly, a welcomed opportunity following the recently confirmed integration phase for KGI. As the session progressed, a participant from one of the consortia joined and used the time to explore practical pathways for connecting with KGI4NFDI, ranging from registration in the KGI registry to potential incubator projects. The idea of a consortium taking an early-mover role in a KGI incubator was discussed as a concrete next step. Questions also touched on the status of EOSC integration, a topic on the roadmap for both TS4NFDI and KGI4NFDI, as well as use cases and data types currently in scope for KGI. The session surfaced relevant next steps and points of contact for consortia interested in engaging with either service.

Related materials:

- GESIS Knowledge Graph: <https://data.gesis.org/gesiskg/site/>

About TS4NFDI

- Service Website: <https://terminology.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- Incubator Overview: <https://terminology.services.base4nfdi.de/incubators>
- Explainer video on [Youtube](#)
- TS4NFDI at Service Roadshow on [Youtube](#)

About KGI4NFDI

- Service Website: <https://kgi.services.base4nfdi.de/>
- KGI4NFDI at Service Roadshow on [Youtube](#)

Room 7 - Communication and Collaboration

The aim of the session was to improve communication and collaboration with Base4NFDI. The external evaluation conducted in 2025 showed that the needs of the consortia and base service teams regarding communication with Base4NFDI vary.

From the perspective of NFDI consortium coordinators, the initially hesitant collaboration is attributed to a lack of technical understanding and the unclear added value of basic services. This has changed with IAM4NFDI, which offers tangible added value and justifies the effort on the behalf of the consortia.

There is a preference for a more product-oriented website. Services and their concrete added value for users should therefore be brought to the fore. A 'how-to' guide for users would be desirable from an end-user perspective, particularly for those with limited technical expertise. An implicit pressure to participate, on the other hand, is counterproductive.

Communication from Base4NFDI should be improved so that the contact persons, who have already been consulted by Base4NFDI on several occasions, are involved in the communication, rather than just the spokesperson and coordinator. Furthermore, the information provided in communications should always be sufficient and understandable even for those with limited technical expertise.

Conclusion: The consortia should be addressed more directly. Future communication should highlight the added value of the basic services.

Related materials:

- 5 Steps to Base4NFDI Service Integration – A Guide for NFDI Consortia, [Zenodo](#)
- Base4NFDI on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/base4nfdi/>